

A Novel AI-LCA Approach for Decontamination of Pharmaceuticals from Water Resources based on Commercial Pumice

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Abstract

The extensive consumption of antibiotics, such as tetracycline (TC), poses significant risks to human health and the environment. Because TC (and other similar antibiotics) bind strongly to minerals, natural minerals have been identified as potential, cost-effective adsorbents for removing antibiotics from aqueous solutions. Hence, pumice was tested as an eco-friendly and cost-effective material for removing TC from water. Batch experiments assessed the effects of essential parameters: pH, contact time, adsorbent dosage, and competing chemicals, including humic acid and phosphate. The TC adsorption kinetics were well described by a Pseudo-Second-Order and Elovich models. The equilibrium results conformed to the Freundlich isotherm model, suggesting multilayer adsorption on a heterogeneous surface. Pumice showed outstanding adsorption capabilities over a wide pH range, reaching up to 97% of TC removal efficiency. Furthermore, the optimization of adsorption by Response Surface Methodology and machine learning models (Artificial Neural Network and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System) revealed robust prediction capabilities, with the Artificial Neural Network displaying enhanced accuracy ($R^2 > 0.98$). This study compares the TC removal effectiveness of pumice with Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). The findings show that CNTs have higher removal efficiency but simultaneously a larger environmental impact. So, pumice is a more affordable and environmentally friendly adsorbent.

Keywords: Tetracycline; Pumice; Artificial Neural Network; Life Cycle Assessment; Green Adsorption

1 Introduction

Concern over environmental contamination is becoming a pressing issue today. One of the most significant environmental problems today is water contamination, which primarily originates from municipal wastewater, veterinary effluents and industrial waste. These effluents commonly contain a wide range of harmful pollutants, including pesticides, heavy metals, drugs [1] and polyfluoroalkyl substances [2]. Many concerns have grown due to the existence of pharmaceutical residues in water sources [3]. Antibiotics, even at low concentrations, can cause damage to human health and the environment *via* bioaccumulation and the development of resistant genes and bacteria [4]. Tetracycline (TC) has been used excessively in medical treatment, aquaculture, and animal husbandry to fight bacterial infections [5]. It has been determined that 30% to 90% of the consumed TC is released into the

environment *via* animal manure and wastewater discharge. Consequently, the concentrations of TC in influent and soil reach a wide range of 1.24–12.34 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and 86–199 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, respectively [6]. The adverse environmental impacts of TC, particularly on aquatic systems, have prompted numerous initiatives to reduce its water and soil concentrations. Moreover, the configuration of TC structures undergoes alterations in response to pH levels. This phenomenon hinders the effectiveness of conventional methodologies, reducing their efficacy [4]. Hence, further studies need to be conducted to develop effective methods across a wide pH range that can also be effective under real-world conditions.

Among the remediation methods, adsorption is a sustainable, economical, environmentally friendly, and often effective method to reduce the concentration of different contaminants, such as TC from the wastewater, and lessen their impact on ecosystems and organisms [4]. Various sorbents like activated carbon [7], zeolite [8], clay minerals [9], and metal–organic frameworks [10] were tested for TC removal. They have emerged as highly efficient adsorbents because of the high cation exchange capability and excellent ionizability [3]. Recent research has extensively examined the TC adsorption by new types of adsorbents, like biochar [11], [12], or Polyvinyl Alcohol-Copper Alginate (PVA-CA) gel beads [13], where the maximum TC adsorption capacity was 231.43 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Silva Bruckmann et al. [4] studied the TC removal using Magnetic Graphene Oxide ($\text{GO}\cdot\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$) from theoretical and experimental approaches. The amount of magnetite integrated on the GO surface, pH, ionic strength, initial TC concentration, adsorbent dosage, temperature, and contact time on adsorption were tested. Under optimal conditions, the maximum adsorption capacity reached 531.93 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Ortiz-Ramos et al. [14] used clays with different structural characteristics, such as bentonite, sepiolite, vermiculite, halloysite, phlogopite and kaolinite. The impact of several factors, including temperature, ionic strength, and pH, on the adsorption capacity was investigated. They found that raw bentonite has the highest adsorption capacity of 283.5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Mei et al. [15] tested Fe–N modified biochar (Fe-N-RSBC) and compared it to other biochar-based materials. The effect of different operating parameters, including pH, ionic types and strength on the adsorptive removal efficiency of TC was studied. The maximum capacity of TC adsorption on Fe-N-RSBC reached 156 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, which was 5.4, 8.2 and 1.9 times higher than that of Pristine Biochar, Urea Modified Biochar, and $\text{FeCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -Modified Biochar, respectively. The studies above mainly used chemically modified and synthesized adsorbents, often requiring energy-intensive preparation. Furthermore, their effectiveness in eliminating TC is significantly influenced by pH, exhibiting optimal performance within a restricted pH range. This limitation considerably reduces their applicability in various environmental conditions. Therefore, developing a straightforward, sustainable adsorbent that can effectively eliminate TC throughout a wide pH range is urgent.

Natural minerals are reasonably priced and have the potential to be used as adsorbents in the remediation of water and wastewater. Pumice, a naturally occurring volcanic rock, is an effective adsorbent owing to its porous structure and low density, showing promising results for removing of heavy metal [16], dye compounds [17], and natural organic matter [17]. One of the primary advantages of granular pumice is its ease of usage in batch and fixed-bed column adsorption systems in a granular form. Moreover, it may be recycled and used again after the proper regeneration methods.

Although pumice, as a natural mineral, presents a viable and economical option for pollutant removal, combining such materials into broader treatment frameworks can further enhance its effectiveness. Constructed Wetlands (CWs) have emerged as a complementary environmentally sustainable technology in this context.

CWs have been identified as an eco-friendly, sustainable and cost-effective approach combining physical, chemical, and biological mechanisms to remediate disparate wastewaters. They have proven efficient in removing antibiotics, pharmaceuticals and personal care products [18], [19]. Wetland plants and microorganisms connected to their root surface and in the rhizosphere absorb nitrogen, phosphorus, and organic carbon from water for their growth and cause a simultaneous denitrification [20]. These systems have shown promising results in the removal of biochemical oxygen demand (66%), total carbon (90%), total suspended solids (62%), fecal coliforms (91%), nitrates (77%), ammonia (53%), heavy metals, and pesticides [21], [22]. Therefore, CWs can act as a barrier and prove a stumbling block for entering these toxic compounds into surface water and reducing their potential impact. However, it is important to note that certain chemicals, such as TC, may decrease treatment efficiency of CWs over time by affecting substrates, plants, and microorganisms, finally impairing their functionality. Incorporating high-adsorption-capacity substrates in CWs, such as zeolite or modified mineral, has enhanced removal effectiveness for antibiotics and other pollutants. For example, Ma et al. [23] assessed the effect of the presence of substrates in CWs on the removal efficiency of antibiotics and Antibiotic Resistance Genes (ARGs). Brick pellets and zeolite were used as adsorbents in their investigation. The results showed that zeolite and brick pellets significantly enhanced antibiotic removal, achieving 73% and 99.15% efficiencies, respectively. Similarly, Du et al. [8] examined the effectiveness of zeolite in removing Sulfonamides (SMs), TC, and associated ARGs, including tetW, tetO, tetM, sul I, sul II, and sul III, from wastewater. The findings revealed that zeolite-based systems demonstrated superior adsorption capacity for SMs.

Despite zeolite's extensive utilization in CWs owing to its significant adsorption capability, it exhibits specific limits that could hinder its wider application. Zeolite is frequently chemically modified to improve its performance, which can raise sustainability issues and operational expenses. Its effectiveness in removing pollutants is also very sensitive to pH, with a limited pH range showing the best results. Because of this, zeolite is less effective in wastewater treatment at extreme or fluctuating conditions. Pumice, in contrast, is a naturally occurring volcanic substance characterized by high porosity and a chemically stable structure. The physical qualities facilitate both the adsorption of pollutants and the colonization of microbial populations, which are crucial for bioremediation processes in CWs [24]. Despite its promising properties, there is still limited information regarding using pumice as a substrate in CWs, particularly for removing antibiotics. Therefore, evaluating the pumice removal efficiency for TC is essential.

This study aims to evaluate the adsorption performance of pumice in TC removal. The effects of various factors, including solution pH, adsorbent mass, and contact time, were investigated to achieve optimal removal efficiency. The impact of other organic matters, such as humic substances and phosphate, standard components existing in CWs environments, was

also examined. Additionally, adsorption kinetics and isotherms were analyzed to elucidate the adsorption mechanism. Notably, for the first time, Response Surface Methodology (RSM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) models were employed to predict pumice performance in TC adsorption from aqueous media. Finally, the application of pumice as an adsorbent is examined, and the comparison is made to other commercial ones by utilizing the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) method.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials

The pumice was supplied by FORESTINA dekor company. Before the application, it was washed with distilled water and dried in an oven. The particle size of dried pumice stone was ~5–12 mm. Tetracycline (98 % purity), hydrochloric acid (37 % purity), and humic sodium salt (technical grade) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Czech Republic. Sodium hydroxide (≥ 97 % purity) and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate were supplied by Honeywell and Lach-Ner company, respectively. All of the chemicals were used without further purification.

2.2 Instruments

A Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) spectrophotometer (NICOLET IZ10, Thermo Scientific, USA) was implemented to determine the pumice functional groups. For this aim, the FT-IR spectrum of pumice was recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

The surface morphology of the pumice (before and after the adsorption process) was studied through Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM, UHR FE-SEM ULTRA Plus, Carl Zeiss, Germany) working at an acceleration voltage of 0.5–2.5 kV equipped with an Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS). EDS spectroscopy and elemental mapping were employed to investigate the elemental composition of pumice.

Pumice's compositional and thermal stability was determined with a Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TGA, TGA/SDTA851e, Mettler Toledo AG, Switzerland). The samples were heated from 30 °C to 800 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere, and the resultant weight loss was recorded. This method identified specific mass loss, including evaporation of physically adsorbed water and the decomposition of organic matter.

The X-ray Diffraction (XRD) pattern of pumice was recorded by a diffractometer (Rigaku, MiniFlex 600) employing $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm at 40 kV and 30 mA) from 10 to 70° with a scanning step of 0.01 degrees/min.

2.3 Batch adsorption experiments

A stock solution of TC containing 10 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ was prepared for the adsorption experiments. The initial pH of the solutions was adjusted to the desired values by adding appropriate amounts of 1 M HCl or 1 M NaOH.

In batch experiments, the impact of the key experimental factors, including pH of the solution (2 to 12), pumice mass (5 to 25 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and 50 to 250 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), and contact time (1 to 300 min) was examined. For each test, a fixed amount of adsorbent was added to 100 mL of a TC

solution (1 mg.L⁻¹) and stirred at 900 rpm. After a specified time, samples were centrifuged (MPW Med. Instruments) and filtered through PTFE syringe filters 0.2 µm (MACHEREY-NAGEL GmbH & Co. KG). The pH of the solution was 7 for the experiments investigating the effect of the pumice mass on the removal of TC.

The initial and final TC concentration was determined by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC, LC/HRMS system, USA). A filtered mobile phase consisting of 0.1% formic acid (phase A) and methanol (phase B) was used for the separation of TC on a Triart C18 column (100 mm × 2.1 mm I. D., 3 µm, YMC CO., LTD., Kyoto, JP), heated to 40 °C. The flow rate was set to 0.42 mL.min⁻¹, and the injection volume was 50 µL. The removal efficiency *RP* (%) and adsorption capacity *q_e* (mg.g⁻¹) were calculated using Eqs. 1 and 2 [25], respectively.

$$RP (\%) = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$q_e = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{M} \times V \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where *C₀* (mg.L⁻¹) and *C_e* (mg.L⁻¹) are initial and final TC concentrations, *V* (L) is the solution volume (100 mL), and *M* (g) is the pumice mass.

2.4 Isotherm studies

For the adsorption isotherm studies, TC solution with varying initial concentrations ranging from 1 to 300 mg.L⁻¹ was prepared. Subsequently, 1.5 g of pumice was added to a flask containing 100 mL of TC solution with initial pH values of 2 and 8 (pumice concentration of 15 g.L⁻¹). An initial pH was set to 8, corresponding to a standard wastewater pH in CWs [26]. Conversely, pH=2 was employed to replicate the highly acidic conditions typical of specific industrial effluents. The mixture was stirred at 900 rpm for 120 min at 25 ± 1 °C. The equilibrium adsorption capacity was then calculated using Eq. 2. Two isotherm models, including Langmuir and Freundlich, were applied to analyze the adsorption mechanism.

2.5 Kinetics studies

The reaction kinetics were studied under the same conditions as the equilibrium studies (15 g.L⁻¹ of pumice, 1 mg.L⁻¹ of TC, initial pH=8, stirring at 900 rpm at 25 ± 1 °C) and time intervals from 1 to 300 min. Four kinetic models were employed: Pseudo-First-Order (PFO), Pseudo-Second-Order (PSO), Intraparticle Diffusion (ID), and Elovich models. The PFO and PSO models were used to evaluate the rate-limiting step of the reaction, while the ID and Elovich models helped to clarify the mass transfer mechanism.

2.6 Competitive adsorption tests

To determine the adsorbent's potential for real-world industrial applications, the pumice's performance in the presence of phosphate and humic acid was assessed. For each test, a specific amount of the adsorbent (15 and 150 g.L⁻¹) was added into 100 mL of the solution containing 1 mg.L⁻¹ of TC at pH=2 and 8. In the binary system with humic acid, the impact of its concentration on TC adsorption was evaluated at three levels: 1, 10, and 100 mg.L⁻¹. For

phosphate, only one concentration of 0.1 mg.L^{-1} was tested. The mixture was stirred for 120 min at 900 rpm, then centrifuged, and filtered using PTFE syringe filters $0.2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

2.7 Optimization and sensitive analysis

In the present study, the most critical factors, including pH, mass of adsorbent, reaction time, and initial concentration, are optimized through RSM modeling in Design Expert 7.0.0 software. In the first step, the experimental data were analyzed as historical data. Subsequently, the collected data bank is assessed by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Based on the ANOVA results, the most significant factors affecting adsorption capacity are identified and evaluated. In the next step, after performing dual sensitivity analysis of the factors on adsorption capacity (q_e), a mathematical model is developed to predict adsorption capacity based on the input variables. Finally, using the RSM method, the optimal values of the influential parameters are computed.

2.8 Machine learning models

In this stage of the present investigation, two models, ANN [27] and ANFIS [28], are assessed for the dynamic prediction of TC decontamination in the water treatment process. This approach aims to enable the adsorption process to operate as a smart system. MATLAB 2019b software is employed to implement both algorithms. For the ANFIS model, the Sugeno method with three membership functions based on the Gaussian 2 model is utilized. The errors in the ANFIS computations are minimized using a hybrid algorithm over 30 epochs. In the ANN modeling, the network type is configured as a Feed-Forward Backpropagation network with the TRAINLM training function. The adaptation learning function, performance function, number of layers, and number of neurons are set as LEARNGDM, Mean Square Error (MSE), 2, and 10, respectively. Additionally, in the ANN computations, the transfer function is defined as TANSIG.

2.9 LCA analysis

The LCA methodology followed ISO 14040/14044 standards [29] with four phases: (1) Goal and scope definition established functional unit of 1 m^3 TC-contaminated water treatment with 90% removal target; (2) Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) compiled research-backed environmental data for pumice mining/processing and carbon nanotube synthesis from peer-reviewed literature; (3) Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) calculated environmental impacts across eight categories (energy, water, CO_2 , SO_x , NO_x , PM2.5, land use, cost) using Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden (Center for Environmental Science at Leiden University, Netherlands) (CML 2001) characterization factors [30]; (4) Interpretation phase analyzed results through normalization, sensitivity analysis, and comparative visualization. MATLAB 2019b [31] was applied for all calculations, statistical analysis, and generating dynamic dashboard animations.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Characterization of pumice

The pumice sample comprises three distinct colors: black, brown, and white. For this reason, FT-IR spectrum of each color was analyzed separately. As illustrated in Fig 1a, the FT-IR

spectrum of the samples revealed four prominent bands at wavenumbers of 408, 534, 720, and 990 cm^{-1} . The band at approximately 990 cm^{-1} indicates the stretching vibration of both Si–O and Al–O [32], [33]. A band at 408 cm^{-1} and the weaker bands at around 534 and 720 cm^{-1} can be assigned to Si–O bending vibrations [34]. An additional band at 1126 cm^{-1} is possibly linked to the stretching vibration of Al–O [35].

Pumice's thermal behavior was investigated using TGA over a temperature range of 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Pumice lost less than 1% of its weight when the temperature increased to 105 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, (It shows that following the adsorption process, certain characteristic peaks of SiO_2 at pH 2, as well as peaks corresponding to both SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 at pH 8, disappear. These spectral changes indicate that TC molecules diffuse into the pores of the pumice and are predominantly adsorbed through chemisorption, which change the original crystalline structure of pumice to amorphous [40].

Fig 1b). It is likely due to the removal of water molecules. This finding is consistent with the endothermic peak of adsorbed moisture elimination. The spectrum exhibits a weight loss of approximately 4.5% between 105 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which may be attributed to volatile organic compounds or temperature-unstable inorganic compounds, e.g., hydrates, hydroxides, carbonates [34]. Overall, the result indicates that pumice contains a relatively low level of organic matter and is temperature stable.

The surface morphology of pumice is depicted in the SEM micrographs in It shows that

following the adsorption process, certain characteristic peaks of SiO_2 at pH 2, as well as peaks corresponding to both SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 at pH 8, disappear. These spectral changes indicate that TC molecules diffuse into the pores of the pumice and are predominantly adsorbed through chemisorption, which change the original crystalline structure of pumice to amorphous [40].

Fig 1c. Pumice has a rough texture with a porous structure characterized by irregular and randomly distributed micropores and a non-uniform plate-like form.

The chemical composition determined by EDS revealed the presence of O (45.7%), Si (26.0%), Al (11.9%), K (5.0%), Fe (4.3%), and minor amounts of Ca (1.2%), Na (1.1%), C (2.1%), N (1.0%), Ti (0.4%), and Mg (0.3%) (Fig. S1b). It suggests it mainly comprises SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 [32], [36].

The XRD pattern of pumice (It shows that following the adsorption process, certain characteristic peaks of SiO_2 at pH 2, as well as peaks corresponding to both SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 at pH 8, disappear. These spectral changes indicate that TC molecules diffuse into the pores of the pumice and are predominantly adsorbed through chemisorption, which change the original crystalline structure of pumice to amorphous [40].

Fig 1d, pink line) reveals clear peaks at 23.50° and 27.72° (2θ), which are linked to dachiardite, a naturally occurring zeolitic mineral with the general formula of $(Ca, Na, K, Mg)_4(Si, Al)_{24}O_{48} \cdot 13H_2O$ [34]. A prominent peak at approximately 20.00° , 29.87° , and 41.65° indicates the presence of quartz (SiO_2) [37], while a smaller peak near 32.37° is attributed to alumina (Al_2O_3) [38]. The XRD patterns after the adsorption process at pH 8 and 2 are shown in Fig 1d. Under acidic conditions (pH 2), slight peak shifts were observed, and no new peaks appeared. In contrast, at pH 8, the XRD pattern displays the appearance of peaks at $2\theta \approx 35.88^\circ$ and 47.11° (highlighted in yellow), suggesting the possible formation of CaO [38] and $Ca(OH)_2$ [39], respectively. It shows that following the adsorption process, certain characteristic peaks of SiO_2 at pH 2, as well as peaks corresponding to both SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 at pH 8, disappear. These spectral changes indicate that TC molecules diffuse into the pores of the pumice and are predominantly adsorbed through chemisorption, which change the original crystalline structure of pumice to amorphous [40].

Fig 1: a) FT-IR spectrum, b) TGA curves, c) SEM of pure pumice, and d) XRD pattern of pumice before and after adsorption in pH 2 and 8

3.2 Effect of pumice mass on TC adsorption

The mass of the adsorbent is a crucial factor affecting adsorption performance, as it directly influences the availability of active sites. Therefore, the effect of different pumice masses on TC removal efficiency was examined. Fig. S2 shows the effect of the adsorbent dosage on TC's adsorption capacity and removal efficiency. While all other parameters (pH: 7, TC concentration: 1 mg.L⁻¹, and time: 300 min) were kept constant, the effects of the adsorbent dosage were investigated in two distinct ranges: 5 to 25 and 50 to 250 g.L⁻¹. Given the lack of sufficient data regarding the influence of pumice dosage on TC removal efficiency and whether it performs better at higher or lower mass loadings, two distinct dosage ranges were considered and experimentally assessed. The findings showed that the removal efficiency of TC improved significantly, rising from 76% to 93% as the adsorbent dose increased from 5 g.L⁻¹ to 15 g.L⁻¹, and from 96% to 99% as the adsorbent dose increased from 50 g.L⁻¹ to 100 g.L⁻¹ but it almost plateaued thereafter (Fig. S2a,c). This improvement is explained by the adsorbent's larger surface area and active binding site availability [41]. The adsorption capacity (Fig. S2b,d) appropriately declined as the adsorbent mass increased and the TC initial amount in the same. This reduction results from an excess of active sites at higher adsorbent dosages, since the fixed amount of TC cannot saturate the available surface [42]. Therefore, pumice masses of 15 (for low dosage) and 150 (for high dosage) g.L⁻¹ were considered as optimal and utilized in the

subsequent experiments.

3.3 Effect of pH on TC adsorption

Since the pH of the solution is a critical parameter influencing adsorption, this study examined TC removal efficiency across a pH range of 2 to 12, namely 2, 4, 7, 10, and 12. Fig. S3 shows the results of experiments with two pumice dosages (15 and 150 g.L⁻¹) and an initial TC concentration of 1 mg.L⁻¹. At the lower dosage (15 g.L⁻¹), removal efficiencies were consistently high (95-99%) across the tested pH range, showing a minor decrease near neutral pH=7. This trend was also reflected in the adsorption capacity, which varied from 0.091 to 0.095 mg.g⁻¹ (Fig. S3a,b). Similarly, the greater pumice dosage (150 g.L⁻¹) demonstrated stable removal performance, with values between 97% and 100% and adsorption capacity ranging from 0.0084 to 0.0086 mg.g⁻¹, again displaying a slight reduction close to neutral pH (Fig. S3 c,d). The results indicate that pumice is a highly effective adsorbent that functions effectively across a broad pH range. The removal efficiency and adsorption capacity exhibit only a minor decrease within the pH range of 7. The pH of 8 was selected for the following experiments in accordance with prior research [26], which demonstrated that the typical pH of wastewater in CWs is approximately 8. Conversely, pH 2 was chosen to replicate highly acidic environments that may be present in specific industrial effluents. Valuable insight into the adsorbent's performance under realistic and extreme conditions is gained by evaluating it under both strongly acidic and alkaline situations, as the pH of wastewater can vary considerably depending on its source.

The pH-dependent adsorption behavior of TC onto pumice is principally due to changes in the adsorbate's ionization state and the adsorbent's surface charge properties. TC is an amphoteric molecule with several ionizable groups, including phenolic and amine functions [43]. At pH < 3.3, TC primarily exists as a protonated cation (TC⁺) due to the complete protonation of the dimethylamino group. In 3.3 < pH < 7.7, it converts to a neutral zwitterionic form (TC) due to the deprotonation of the hydroxyl group in the tricarbonyl system with an acylamino group. At 7.7 < pH < 9.7 and above 9.7, it exists as monoanionic (TC⁻) and dianionic (TC²⁻) species, resulting from the deprotonation of the phenolic diketone system and the dimethylamino group, respectively [6], [44], [45].

The surface of pumice is affected by pH, displaying protonated hydroxyl groups ($\equiv\text{SiOH}_2^+$) in acidic conditions and deprotonated forms ($\equiv\text{SiO}^-$) in alkaline environments [46], as illustrated in Eqs. 3 and 4.

In acidic conditions, cation exchange between TC⁺ and protonated silica groups ($\equiv\text{SiOH}_2^+$), combined with hydrogen bonding between TC functional groups and surface hydroxyl groups, mostly governs TC uptake [47], [48]. As the pH enhances toward neutrality (pH 4–7), the pumice surface loses its positive charge and TC exists in its zwitterionic form (TC₂), hence reducing the intensity of both electrostatic and cation exchange interactions. This tends to slightly reduce TC adsorption, as observed [3]. However, in alkaline conditions (pH values

higher than 8), the adsorption of TC by pumice increased. This could be attributed to hydrogen bonding between TC functional moieties and residual SiOH on the surface of the pumice and as well as cationic bridging interactions between TC molecules and metal ions such as Fe, Al, and Mg present in the pumice [44], [49], [50].

Further, Fig. S1 and Fig. S4 – S6 display SEM micrographs and elemental distribution mapping of pumice samples before adsorption and after adsorption of TC at pH 2 and pH 8. As previously stated, before adsorption (Fig. S1a), the pumice surface exhibits significant porosity, roughness, and irregularity, reflecting its natural volcanic origin. These morphological characteristics suggest a high surface area and accessibility of active sites, which are beneficial for adsorption. Following TC adsorption at pH 2 and 8 (Fig. S1c,e), the surface morphology changes. The pores appear partially filled, and a layer of surface deposits has formed, indicating adsorption. The diminished roughness suggests that TC molecules have interacted with the surface, likely *via* hydrogen bonding and cation exchange. The possible mechanism for TC adsorption onto pumice is shown in Fig 2.

As discussed in Section 3.1, the pumice XRD pattern at pH 2 shows only a slight shift. This may imply that the pumice surface is protonated and that some cation leaching probably takes place in acidic environments. These changes, along with the decreased peak intensity, suggest that TC has been adsorbed onto the pumice surface. In contrast, the XRD pattern of pumice at pH 8 exhibits more pronounced peak shifts and the formation of CaO [38], and Ca(OH)₂ [51], implying that TC adsorption also takes place under alkaline conditions. The appearance of new peaks might result from precipitation of TC via cationic bonding bridge (such as TC–Ca²⁺) on the pumice, stabilizing the structure [39]. Furthermore, the peak observed related to the Ca(OH)₂, may indicate that TC is adsorbed through hydrogen bonding in an alkaline environment where hydroxyl groups are more reactive.

Previous studies indicate that the optimal pH for TC and even other antibiotics like Sulfathiazole (STZ) removal typically resides in the acidic range, with maximum removal efficiency reported around pH 2–3 [51], [52]. The pH of the solution heavily influences the efficiency of adsorption processes, since it significantly impacts the surface charge of the adsorbent and the ionization state of the adsorbate. Nevertheless, pumice exhibited a distinctly different behavior in this regard. Unlike many commonly used adsorbents, pumice maintained a relatively consistent adsorption capacity for TC across a wide pH range. This pH-independent performance is a substantial advantage, as the pH of real industrial wastewater frequently fluctuates depending on the effluent source. Therefore, pumice is a promising candidate for real-world wastewater treatment.

Fig 2: Possible mechanism for TC adsorption on pumice surface

3.4 Effect of contact time on TC adsorption

Contact time is a critical operational parameter in adsorption processes, as it determines the duration of interaction between the adsorbate and the adsorbent, significantly affecting removal efficiency. Fig. S7 illustrates the effect of contact time (1 to 300 min) on the removal efficiency of TC from aqueous solution with an initial concentration of $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, pH 8, and dosage of $15 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The findings showed a rapid initial adsorption, with approximately 65% of TC removed within the first 5 min. This rapid uptake can be attributed to a high concentration gradient between the bulk solution and the pumice surface, which promotes fast external surface adsorption [53]. The removal efficiency increased consistently, attaining a maximum of 98% at 120 min. This phase likely involved gradual pore diffusion into the internal structure of the pumice [53]. Beyond this point, a slight decline of about 4% in removal efficiency was observed. This reduction may be due to the restricted available active sites, saturation of the adsorbent surface, or partial desorption of previously adsorbed TC molecules due to pH shift [54], [55]. Therefore, based on these results, the optimum contact time for effective TC removal using pumice under the given conditions was determined to be 120 min.

3.5 Isotherm study

Two isotherm models were employed to analyze the adsorption mechanism and evaluate the affinity of TC for pumice: Langmuir and Freundlich. The experimental equilibrium data were fitted using these models, and the optimal model was determined based on the determination coefficient (R^2). The isotherm study was performed at two distinct pH levels: pH 2, representing the acidic conditions for TC removal, and pH 8, reflecting a more realistic environmental context.

3.5.1 Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm study

The linear forms of the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms are presented in Table S1 as Eq. S1 and Eq. S2, respectively. As shown in Fig. S8a (pH 2) and Fig. S9a (pH 8), the Langmuir constant (k_L) and maximum monolayer adsorption capacity (q_{max}) were determined from the plot of C_e/q_e vs. C_e [35]. The Freundlich constants (n and k_F) for pH 2 and 8 were obtained from the linear plot of $\text{Log } q_e$ vs. $\text{Log } C_e$ [35] (Fig. S8b and Fig. S9b), with the fitting parameters summarized in Table 1. According to the Langmuir model, the q_{max} at pH 8 is higher than at pH 2; however, due to the lower R^2 value, this q_{max} estimate is not reliable. The Freundlich model demonstrated a significantly better fit to the equilibrium adsorption data, evidenced by higher determination coefficients ($R^2 = 0.973$ for pH 2 and $R^2 = 0.965$ for pH 8) compared to the Langmuir model ($R^2 = 0.875$ for pH 2 and $R^2 = 0.750$ for pH 8). These results suggest that the adsorption process is non-linear, likely due to heterogeneous adsorption sites on pumice. TC initially adsorbs onto high-energy sites, followed by gradual adsorption onto lower-energy sites [56]. The $1/n$ values, indicative of adsorption intensity, were 0.450 and 0.635 for pH 2 and 8, respectively, below 1, thereby showing heterogeneous adsorption sites through multilayer formation [57]. The lower $1/n$ ratio at pH 2, closer to zero, suggests that the surface properties of pumice vary significantly in acidic and alkaline conditions [35].

Table 2 compares the TC adsorption capacity for the pumice (based on Langmuir model) with antibiotics removal, mainly TC, on other types of adsorbents. Pumice has about the same maximum adsorption capacity as other adsorbents made from waste products. In some cases, the surfaces of the adsorbents were chemically modified. This highlights one of pumice's main advantages over modified adsorbents. The manufacturing and application of modified adsorbents frequently entail chemical processes that could discharge toxic materials into the environment. Furthermore, the adsorbents utilized in those studies were in powdered form, thereby restricting their practical application in fixed-bed columns. Following the adsorption process, several mechanical separation steps are necessary to recover powdered adsorbents from the treated water. This adds complexity and increases operational expenses. In contrast, pumice, with its granular structure, can be easily applied in column systems without the need for additional separation processes, making it a more practical and cost-effective alternative for large-scale water treatment.

Table 1: The isotherm parameters for the adsorption of TC on pumice, Condition: TC initial concentration: 1 - 300 mg.L⁻¹, pH: 2 and 8, M_p: 15 g.L⁻¹, 900 rpm

Isotherm model	Isotherm constant	Determination coefficient
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Optimal pH 2			
Langmuir	q_{max} (mg.g ⁻¹)	k_L (L.mg ⁻¹)	R^2
	2.967	0.052	0.875
Freundlich	n	k_F	R^2
	2.222	0.316	0.973
Operational pH 8			
Langmuir	q_{max} (mg.g ⁻¹)	k_L (L.mg ⁻¹)	R^2
	4.166	0.024	0.750
Freundlich	n	k_F	R^2
	1.574	0.167	0.965

Table 2: Comparison of TC adsorption by various adsorbents

Adsorbent	Adsorbate	q_{max} (mg.g⁻¹)	References
Present work	TC	2.967 for pH 2 4.166 for pH 8	
Modified coal fly ash	Ciprofloxacin	1.547	[58]
Porous carbon derived from Salix psammophila	TC	2.710	[59]
Citosan/Olive pomace film	TC	1.600	[60]
Surfactant modified hazelnut shell	TC	6.970	[61]
Ben/Rm/Ps-op ceramsite	TC	2.560	[62]

3.6 Kinetics study

To further investigate the adsorption mechanism and identify the rate-limiting step, four kinetic models were applied: PFO, PSO, ID, and Elovich. The suitability of each model was evaluated by comparing the determination coefficients (R^2) and the agreement between the

calculated equilibrium adsorption capacity and the experimental data ($q_{e,exp}$). The model that showed the highest R^2 value and the closest fit to the experimental data was considered the most appropriate for describing the adsorption kinetics.

3.6.1 PFO and PSO kinetic models

The data was analyzed using the linear form of the PFO and PSO, which are shown in Table S2 as Eq. S3 and Eq. S4, respectively. As illustrated in Fig. S10a, the linear plot of $\ln(q_e - q_t)$ vs. t was used to compute the PFO constant rate (k_1) and q_e values [35]. Similarly, the linear plot of the t/q_t vs. t was used to calculate the PSO constant rate (k_2) and q_e values [35], shown in Fig. S10b. According to the parameters shown in Table 3, R^2 and q_e for the PFO were 0.506 and 0.018 mg.g⁻¹, respectively, while R^2 and q_e for the PSO were 0.998 and 0.056 mg.g⁻¹, respectively. By a comparison of the R^2 values for two models, the PSO offers a significantly better fit to the data than the PFO. The q_e value derived from PSO model favorably explains the sorption of TC on pumice and is in good agreement with the $q_{e,exp}$ data which is 0.056 mg.g⁻¹. This indicates that a chemical mechanism is mostly responsible for controlling the overall rate-limiting step for the TC adsorption [63], [64].

3.6.2 ID kinetic model

The diffusive mass transfer-based ID model, which is displayed in Eq. S5 (Table S2) provides a link between q_t and the ID rate (k_i) [65]. As shown in Fig. S10c, k_i and the constant C can be found by plotting q_t vs. $t^{1/2}$ [35]. The constant C is associated with the thickness of the boundary layer, which is directly proportional to the influence of the boundary layer. The ID model cannot be regarded as the sole rate-limiting step for TC adsorption, based on the data in Table 3. The deviation of the graph from the origin suggests that other mechanisms are involved in regulating the adsorption rate [65].

3.6.3 Elovich kinetic model

The Elovich model, a widely used model for describing chemisorption, was employed in this study and is presented as Eq. S6 in Table S2. The model presumes that the active sites of the adsorbent are heterogeneous, leading to a range of activation energies for chemisorption [66]. The initial adsorption rate (A) and the desorption constant (B) were determined by plotting $\ln t$ vs. q_t [67], as illustrated in Fig. S10d. Based on the R^2 value provided in Table 3, the Elovich model is ranked as the second-best fit, following the PSO model. The value of A , which indicates the availability of active sites for the adsorption process [67], was calculated to be 2.463 (mg.g⁻¹.min⁻¹).

Table 3: The kinetic parameters for the adsorption of TC on pumice, Condition: TC initial concentration: 1 mg.L⁻¹, pH: 8, M_p: 15 g.L⁻¹, 900 rpm

Kinetic model	Kinetic constant		Determination coefficient
	k_1 (min ⁻¹)	q_e (mg.g ⁻¹)	R^2
PFO	0.027	0.018	0.506

PSO	k_2 (g.mg ⁻¹ .min ⁻¹)	q_e (mg.g ⁻¹)	R^2	H
	8.264	0.056	0.998	0.121
ID	k_i (mg.g ⁻¹ .min ^{-1/2})	C (mg.g ⁻¹)	R^2	
	0.001	0.036	0.635	
Elovich	A (mg.g ⁻¹ .min ⁻¹)	B (g.mg ⁻¹)	R^2	
	2.463	200	0.831	

3.7 Competitive adsorption

An investigation was conducted to assess the interactive effects of common inhibitory substances, specifically humic acid (HA) and phosphate, on the adsorption performance of pumice for TC removal. The effect of HA on TC adsorption was evaluated at HA concentrations of 1, 10, and 100 mg.L⁻¹, and compared with a blank experiment without HA (pH 2 and 8, TC initial concentration of 1 mg.L⁻¹, adsorbent dosages of 15 and 150 g.L⁻¹). According to Fig 3a HA negatively impacted TC adsorption at both pH levels. As its concentration increased from 1 to 100 mg.L⁻¹, the adsorption of TC diminished significantly, presumably due to competitive adsorption for surface sites [68] and blockage of active sites by humic macromolecules [69]. The adsorption capacity of TC in the presence of HA is lower at pH 8 than at pH 2. Nevertheless, at higher adsorbent dosages, this negative effect was less significant (Fig 3c), suggesting that the increased availability of surface area can partially mitigate the inhibitory influence of HA on TC adsorption [41]. Under acidic conditions, the removal of TC in the presence of HA is greater than under alkaline conditions. At low pH, TC predominantly exists in its protonated form (TC⁺), while the functional groups of HA become increasingly deprotonated, resulting in a higher density of negative charges on HA molecules [6]. Simultaneously, the pumice surface is protonated, forming positively charged ≡SiOH₂⁺ groups. These electrostatic interactions favor the formation of HA–TC complexes and enhance the adsorption of TC compared to alkaline conditions.

However, some studies have reported enhanced TC adsorption at specific HA concentrations, due to the formation of HA–TC complexes that act as molecular bridges, facilitating the interaction between TC and the adsorbent surface (e.g., *via* π–π interactions or hydrogen bonding). In such cases, HA can play a dual role: competitor and simultaneously an intermediary linking the antibiotic molecules to the surface [70], [71], [72].

Phosphate also exerted an inhibitory effect on TC adsorption across all tested conditions (Fig 3d,e). The negative impact of phosphate was especially notable at alkaline pH (8) and lower adsorbent dosage (15 g.L⁻¹), where electrostatic repulsion between negatively charged TC, phosphate ions, and the pumice surface intensified competition for adsorption sites [73]. As with HA, higher adsorbent dosages mitigated phosphate's inhibitory influence by providing increased surface area and a number of adsorption sites (Fig 3f) [41].

Fig 3: The outcomes of the presence of the HA and phosphate based on a) HA initial concentration 1, 10, 100 mg.L⁻¹, pH: 2 and 8, b) pH: 2 and 8, M_p : 15 and 150 g.L⁻¹, c) HA initial concentration 1, 10, 100 mg.L⁻¹, M_p : 15 and 150 g.L⁻¹, d) phosphate initial concentration 0.1 mg.L⁻¹, pH: 2 and 8 e) pH: 2 and 8, M_p : 15 and 150 g.L⁻¹, and f) phosphate initial concentration 0.1 mg.L⁻¹, M_p : 15 and 150 g.L⁻¹, Condition: TC initial concentration: 1 mg.L⁻¹, t: 120 min, 900 rpm

3.8 Statistical optimization

The results of statistical optimization modeling based on historical data analysis using the RSM model are presented below. As shown in Fig. S11a, the plot of actual vs. predicted values

based on the quadratic model (Eq. S7) exhibits a linear relationship, indicating good model performance, which is further supported by the statistical indicators listed in Table. S3. Moreover, in Fig. S11b demonstrates that the response variable (adsorption capacity) is approximately normally distributed, consistent with a linear Gaussian statistical model.

According to the results presented in Table S3, the quadratic model was statistically significant with $R^2 \approx 0.992$ and predicted- $R^2 \approx 0.973$, indicating excellent agreement between experimental and predicted values. Therefore, this model was selected for further analysis in the present study. However, the RSM approach is not intended for real-time operational control; consequently, in the next stage, a data-driven machine learning model was developed to enable early-stage decision-making in the adsorption process. As shown in Table 4, ANOVA results confirm that the model is highly significant overall ($F=239.16$, $p < 0.0001$). Among the individual terms, the quadratic effect of initial concentration (D^2) had the strongest influence on adsorption capacity ($F=128.88$, $p < 0.0001$), followed by the interaction between pH and initial concentration (BD) ($F=4.32$, $p=0.047$). Main effects of mass (A), pH (B), and time (C) were not statistically significant at $\alpha=0.05$. However, among the single factors, pH, with the highest F-value (2.88) and the lowest P-value (0.101), was identified as the most significant factor influencing the adsorption of TC onto pumice. The response surface plots in Fig 4 illustrate that IC and its interaction with pH drive strong non-linear effects on adsorption capacity, whereas other factor interactions are closer to linear. Overall, the quadratic model successfully captures the combined influence of operational parameters on the adsorption process.

Azizi et al. [74] studied the removal efficiency of Amoxicillin (AMX) using cellular lightweight concrete as an adsorbent. The effects of key parameters, including contact time, adsorbent dosage, and solution pH, were studied. In addition to experimental assessments, three main parameters were selected for optimization of the adsorption process using the RSM-CCD. These factors were pH (A), adsorbent dosage (B), and contact time (C). The results indicated that the solution pH had a significant impact on the adsorption capacity, primarily due to its direct influence on the surface charge of the adsorbent and the contaminant. Yousefi et al. [75] proposed predictive modeling approaches for the removal of Ciprofloxacin (CIP) from aqueous solutions using Magnetized Functionalized Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (FMWCNTs- Fe_3O_4) as the adsorbent. To develop accurate models, they applied RSM and Support Vector Regression (SVR). The study examined the effects of several key variables, including solution pH, adsorbent dosage, contact time, and initial CIP concentration. Among these factors, pH had the most pronounced influence on adsorption capacity, as supported by the highest F-value and lowest P-value in the RSM analysis. These findings demonstrate that the results obtained in the present study are consistent with those reported in previous research.

Table 4: The outcomes of ANOVA assessment in the present study

Source	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F Value	p-value Prob > F
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Model	26.804	2.061	239.161	< 0.0001	significant
A-Mass	4.777×10^{-5}	4.777×10^{-5}	0.005	0.941	
B-pH	0.024	0.024	2.887	0.101	
C-time	3.827×10^{-5}	3.827×10^{-5}	0.004	0.947	
D-IC	3.126×10^{-5}	3.126×10^{-5}	0.003	0.952	
AB	8.170×10^{-7}	8.170×10^{-7}	9.477×10^{-5}	0.992	
AC	0				
AD	4.490×10^{-5}	4.490×10^{-5}	0.005	0.943	
BC	0.0004	0.0004	0.054	0.817	
BD	0.037	0.037	4.326	0.047	
CD	3.566×10^{-5}	3.566×10^{-5}	0.004	0.949	
A²	0.002	0.002	0.288	0.595	
B²	7.730×10^{-6}	7.730×10^{-6}	0.0008	0.976	
C²	8.017×10^{-6}	8.017×10^{-6}	0.0009	0.975	
D²	1.111	1.111	128.884	< 0.0001	
Residual	0.215	0.008			
Cor Total	27.019				

Fig 4: The results of sensitive analysis based on a) mass-pH vs. q_e , b) mass-time vs. q_e , c) mass-IC vs. q_e , d) pH-time vs. q_e , e) pH-IC vs. q_e , and f) time-IC vs. q_e

Table 5 summarizes the optimal conditions for achieving the highest adsorption capacity. The data indicated that under acidic conditions (pH=2), with an IC of 100 mg.L⁻¹, the lowest amount of the adsorbent, and a reaction time of approximately 200 min, a high adsorption capacity was attained. In contrast, under alkaline conditions (pH > 10), achieving the same amount of the adsorption capacity requires at least four times more adsorbent.

Table 5: The optimal suggestions of RSM model based on input variables and the highest adsorption capacity amounts

Number	Mass (g)	pH	Time (min)	IC (mg.L ⁻¹)	q_e (mg.g ⁻¹)	Desirability
1	79.14	10.78	296.56	141.25	3.181	1
2	11.49	2.23	210.69	104.68	3.024	1

3	47.07	11.3	177.68	143.38	3.015	1
4	49.94	11.88	295.69	104.56	3.309	1
5	34.26	4.85	269.49	114.1	3.227	1
6	5.1	5.23	200.15	99.12	3.084	1

Fig. S12 illustrates the desirability of the developed model and the adsorption capacity under optimal conditions. As shown in Fig. S12a, the model exhibits the highest desirability at lower adsorbent dosages. Fig. S12b demonstrated that maximum adsorption capacity can be achieved under varying conditions, depending on the interaction between pH and adsorbent mass. Under acidic conditions, a lower adsorbent dosage is sufficient, whereas in alkaline conditions, a higher mass of adsorbent is required to achieve similar adsorption performance.

3.9 Machine learning modelling

Fig. S13 depicted the complete framework and learning dynamics of the ANFIS employed to forecast the adsorption capacity based on multiple process parameters. Fig. S13a illustrates the complete structure of the ANFIS model. Different input factors, including initial concentration, pH, time, and Mass, are depicted in yellow blocks and linked to the Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) module. This FIS component constitutes the decision-making core by integrating fuzzy logic with adaptive functionalities. The model analyzes these inputs and generates the adsorption capacity as the final result, depicted in the blue block. Fig. S13b illustrates the membership function plots for a chosen input factor. It shows the system's interpretation of input using fuzzy sets like "low," "medium," and "high," employing overlapping Gaussian functions. This stage is crucial for transforming numerical inputs into language values, enabling the system to manage uncertainty and non-linear interactions efficiently. Fig. S13c presents a comprehensive illustration of the ANFIS network structure. The multilayered structure comprises an input layer, a rule (hidden) layer depicted in blue, and an output layer. Each rule node signifies a fuzzy rule formed from the input factors, while the dense connections illustrate the model's logical synthesis. The use of logical operators like AND, OR, and NOT is shown in the legend, demonstrating how the system integrates several fuzzy conditions to estimate outputs. Fig. S13d depicts the training error throughout 30 epochs. The declining trend of the error numbers indicates that the model effectively reduces prediction error as it learns from the data. This convergence behavior highlights the robustness and precision of the ANFIS model during the training phase.

Fig. S14a–f displays three-dimensional surface plots generated from the ANFIS model, demonstrating the interaction impacts of pairs of input parameters on the estimated adsorption capacity. In Fig. S14a, an increase in input1 (Mass) results in elevated output values, whereas input2 (pH) has a stabilizing effect. Fig. S14b illustrates a pronounced peak indicating that moderate levels of input1 (Mass) and input3 (time) yield optimum adsorption. Fig. S14c illustrates a significant decrease in output when input4 (IC) increases, demonstrating its adverse effect regardless of input1 (Mass). Fig. S14d demonstrates a dome-shaped surface for input2

(pH) and input3 (time), indicating that their optimal mid-range values facilitate adsorption. Fig. S14e additionally illustrates a significant center elevation, where concurrent mid-range values of input2 (pH) and input4 (IC) produce enhanced outcomes. Ultimately, Fig. S14f demonstrates that input3 (time) exerts a significant positive impact on the output, whereas input4 (IC) has minimal effect in this context.

Fig. S15a–c depicts the diagnostic assessment and predictive efficacy of the regression model, along with the statistical results shown in Table 6. These representations facilitate the evaluation of the model's validity, fit, and predictive capacity throughout the dataset. Fig. S15a illustrates the residuals vs. the output factor, indicating the divergence of actual values from the fitted regression line. The distribution of residuals around zero indicates acceptable homoscedasticity; however, some clustering suggests possible non-linear patterns. Fig. S15b compares the actual adsorption capacity (Y) with the predicted adsorption capacity (predicted Y). The alignment of the orange squares (predicted values) with the blue diamonds (observed values) suggests that the model offers a weak prediction of the response variable within the observed data range. Fig. S15c illustrates the normal probability plot of the response variable across sample percentiles. Table 6 summarizes the regression data, showing a Multiple R of 0.823 and an R^2 of 0.678, which indicates that about 67.8% of the variance in the response variable is accounted for by the model. The adjusted R^2 of 0.645 accounts for the number of predictors included, and the low standard error (0.0136) indicates a narrow data dispersion around the regression line, thus affirming the model's suitability. Nonetheless, the ANFIS model, with an R^2 of 0.678, is inapplicable due to the prediction methodology. Consequently, the subsequent stage will involve an analysis of the performance of an ANN model.

Table 6: The regression analysis of ANFIS algorithm for prediction of adsorption capacity values

Regression	Statistics
Multiple R	0.823
R Square	0.677
Adjusted R Square	0.645
Standard Error	0.013
Observations	12

In the next stage, Fig. S16a shows the ANN structure with 4 input neurons, one hidden layer of 10 neurons, and a single output. Fig. S16b illustrates the training performance, where the best validation error (0.014768) is achieved at epoch 2, which indicates fast convergence and reliable model generalization.

Fig. S17a illustrates the trend of gradient reduction, achieving a value of 0.012655 at epoch 8, signifying the stabilization of learning. Fig. S17b depicts the adaptive learning rate (μ),

which diminishes to 0.0001 by epoch 3 and remains constant, facilitating convergence. Fig. S17c displays validation checks, attaining the stopping limit (6) at epoch 8, indicating early stopping to prevent overfitting.

Fig. S18a–d shows high correlation between predicted and actual values across training ($R=0.995$), validation ($R=0.991$), test ($R=0.999$), and overall ($R=0.988$) datasets, confirming excellent ANN performance. Compared to ANFIS ($R=0.823$), the ANN model exhibits stronger predictive accuracy, making it more suitable for real-time or online decision-making systems where precision and rapid adaptation are essential.

Dolatabadi et al. [76] investigated the efficiency of TC removal using modified zeolite, employing predictive modeling through ANN and the ANFIS. Among the tested configurations, the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm demonstrated the lowest prediction error and was identified as the optimal network structure. The comparison of conventional error functions for ANN and ANFIS revealed that the ANN model provided results within an acceptable error range and showed strong agreement with experimental data. Similarly, Firouzi et al. [77] explored a hybrid approach involving simultaneous adsorption and photocatalytic degradation of TC using CdS/TiO₂ nanosheets/graphene nanocomposites. Their study also assessed the modeling capabilities of ANN and ANFIS for predicting TC removal efficiency. Both ANN and ANFIS models demonstrated high predictive accuracy, with results closely matching the experimental data, indicating their suitability for forecasting TC removal performance.

According to the results of ANN model, a Decision Support System (DSS) can be developed due to the smart operation of TC contamination in water treatment plants. The input data can be sent to the DSS by different sensors, including online pH meter, reactor timer, online concentration analyzer, and mass injector gauges. Therefore, in the adsorptive reactor, the ultimate capacity could be controlled just with Application Programming Interface (API) of input variables and ANN-based adsorption capacity predictions. Likewise, Arab et al. [78] suggested the same soft-sensor framework in the coagulation procedure, which could be implemented in water treatment plants. Plus, in the approach, after prediction of adsorption capacity based on the sensor data, with the application of some threshold levels, the obtained values can be categorized as an acceptable or non-acceptable range of performance. Therefore, the process can be justified in desirable operational conditions as per input variable fluctuations through the adsorption.

3.10 Life Cycle Assessment

This study incorporates several key environmental impact assumptions derived from LCA literature. For pumice processing, the model assumes primary energy consumption of 19.34 MJ.kg⁻¹, CO₂ emissions of 0.646 kg CO₂ eq.kg⁻¹, acidification potential of 0.000921 kg SO₂ eq.kg⁻¹, and eutrophication potential of 1.86×10⁻⁴ kg PO₄ eq.kg⁻¹ based on wet grinding process data [79]. Also, according to the results of the present study, water consumption is considered equal to 0.1 L.kg⁻¹. Natural pozzolan concrete is assumed to provide approximately 15% lower global warming potential compared to ordinary Portland cement concrete, validating its environmental benefits as a sustainable alternative [80]. For CNT production, the model assumes commercial-scale CO₂ emissions of 210 kg CO₂ eq.kg⁻¹ for high-purity CNTs

synthesized *via* chemical vapor deposition [81]. Additionally, the energy intensity of high-purity CNT production is assumed to be $6.3 \times 10^4 \text{ MJ.kg}^{-1}$, representing the substantial energy requirements associated with this manufacturing process. The environmental impacts of a Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) synthesis are incorporated into the model assumptions, accounting for both direct energy consumption during synthesis and the indirect impacts from required infrastructure [82]. CNT production under energy-intensive conditions consumes 63000 MJ.kg^{-1} (Production cost: 49000 MJ.kg^{-1} + Operational cost: 14000 MJ.kg^{-1}) [82] and 0.115 L.kg^{-1} of water [81]. It emits $5500 \text{ kg SO}_2 \text{ eq.kg}^{-1}$, $80 \text{ kg NO}_x \text{ eq.kg}^{-1}$, and $100 \text{ kg PM}_{2.5} \text{ eq.kg}^{-1}$ [83]. These items reflect high-emission scenarios typical of lab-scale or poorly optimized CVD processes using fossil-based energy with limited mitigation controls. These comprehensive assumptions enable a thorough environmental assessment of the proposed material systems and processing methods. Other assumptions and computational parameters are set based on Table. S4.

A comparative LCA result comparing the economic and environmental effects of employing CNTs and pumice for TC adsorption at different starting concentrations ($10\text{--}100 \text{ mg.L}^{-1}$) is shown in Fig. S19. The sensitivity of CO_2 emissions to TC concentration is shown in Fig. S19a, and the related cost is examined in Fig. 19b. The CO_2 emissions from CNTs show a significant linear rise with increasing TC concentrations in Fig. S19a, around $40 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ eq}$ at 100 mg.L^{-1} of TC. Pumice, on the other hand, has very low emissions, staying below $25 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ eq}$ across the whole concentration range. This implies that pumice provide notable benefits in lowering greenhouse gas emissions per unit of adsorption, even though CNTs has a larger environmental impact, maybe as a result of its bulk material utilization or processing needs. From an economic perspective, the tendency is reversed in Fig. S19b. Costs for CNTs are significantly higher, ranging from about \$10 to \$75 USD, depending on the concentration. Pumice, on the other hand, continues to be economically advantageous, with prices rising more moderately from about \$2 to \$15 USD.

CNTs and pumice are contrasted in Fig. S20 using normalized values. CNTs have a substantially higher Global Warming Potential (GWP), Acidification (AP) and Eutrophication Potential (EP) than pumice which is demonstrated in Fig. S20a. In Fig. S20b, CNTs demonstrate superior adsorption effectiveness by outperforming pumice in adsorption capacity and surface area, while requiring substantially less mass for the same decontamination task, despite their higher environmental trade-offs. Conversely, pumice exhibits lower environmental impacts, making it a potentially greener adsorbent option.

The environmental effect ratios of CNTs to pumice are shown in Fig. S21a. The CNTs have very high values, particularly in SO_x ($37208.3\times$), NO_x ($2679.9\times$), and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ ($311.5\times$) emissions, while the CO_2 and water impacts are quite small. The contribution of each material to overall environmental loads is shown in Fig. S21b, where CNTs considerably contribute to SO_x emissions while pumice dominates energy usage. Normalized impact values are displayed in Fig. S21c, which reveals that while pumice has higher normalized values in water and land use, CNTs have higher impacts in most categories, especially SO_x , NO_x , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, and energy. Despite the performance advantages of CNTs, this comparison highlights their environmental cost.

Absolute impact values are shown in Fig 5a, where CNTs exhibit noticeably higher values, particularly in the areas of energy, cost, and gaseous emissions. The majority of impact indicators are dominated by CNTs, as shown by Fig 5b, which normalizes these values by their maximum in each category. Once more highlighting the increased influence of CNTs, particularly for SO_x and NO_x , Fig 5c normalizes the data using pumice as the baseline. CNTs continue to score close to 1 for the majority of impacts, showing their comparatively larger environmental burden, when min–max normalization is applied across all categories in Fig 5d. The contrast is shown graphically in Fig 5e, a radar chart: pumice only dominates in water and land use effects, whereas CNTs cluster in high impact zones. Last but not least, Fig 5f illustrates all effects on a logarithmic scale, distinctly differentiating orders of magnitude in energy consumption and emissions, confirming that CNTs have a substantially larger environmental impact than pumice.

Fig 5: Comparative assessment of pumice and CNTs using a) absolute values, b) normalization by maximum, c) normalization by pumice baseline, d) min–max normalization, e) radar chart, and f) logarithmic scale

Fig. S22 presents the sensitivity analysis of dynamic input variables and their influence on environmental impacts for pumice and CNTs, with the process evolution detailed in Video A.1. Fig. S22a shows the normalized values of key input variables TC concentration ($10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), treatment volume (50 m^3), and removal target (95%), highlighting the dominance of removal efficiency in system performance. In Fig. S22b, CNTs exhibit significantly higher scaled environmental impacts, particularly in SO_x emissions, compared to pumice. Fig. S22c quantifies these differences, showing impact ratios such as $20\times$ for energy, $5\times$ for cost, and a peak of $37208\times$ for SO_x . Fig. S22 illustrates a specific scenario, while the attached video (Video A.1) demonstrates the procedure and results under varying conditions.

A stepped pattern of concentration, volume, and removal target changes during the simulated treatment is shown in Fig. S22d, which shows how the input variables vary over

time. The time evolution of several impacts on a logarithmic scale is shown in Fig. S22e, which shows how changes in input conditions affect the cost and energy consumption of both materials. The full impact profile is finally summarized in a radar chart in Fig. S22f, which further supports the fact that CNTs have a greater overall environmental load than pumice in all significant categories. This methodology for dynamic evaluation sheds light on the direct relationship between operational goals and sustainability results. The developed technique can be integrated with machine learning models to function as an online predictive DSS, enabling real-time optimization and control of TC decontamination processes using pumice as the adsorbent.

4 Conclusion

This study effectively assessed commercial pumice as an economical, eco-friendly adsorbent for the elimination of TC. Its adsorption performance was assessed under various operational conditions in a batch system. The results demonstrated that pumice is an effective and viable adsorbent for TC removal, performing efficiently across a wide pH range. Notably, it achieved removal efficiencies exceeding 97% under the selected operational conditions at pH 2 and pH 8. The presence of humic acid and phosphate slightly reduced adsorption efficiency, particularly under alkaline conditions; however, this effect was mitigated by increasing the pumice dosage. These findings support the suitability of pumice for practical water treatment applications, including its potential integration into CWs. The equilibrium data fitted well to the Freundlich isotherm model, with $R^2=0.973$ at pH 2 and $R^2=0.965$ at pH 8, indicating multilayer adsorption on a heterogeneous surface. The maximum adsorption capacities, based on the Langmuir model, were $2.967 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at pH 2 and $4.166 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at pH 8. Optimization using the RSM identified the optimal conditions as: pH 2.23, adsorbent dose 11.49 g, time 210.69 min, and IC $104.68 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, yielding a maximum adsorption capacity of $3.024 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. According to the ANOVA results, solution pH had the most significant influence on TC removal efficiency. Furthermore, machine learning models, including ANN and ANFIS, were employed to predict and optimize adsorption performance. Among these, the ANN model exhibited superior predictive accuracy ($R^2>0.988$), highlighting its potential as a robust tool for process optimization and intelligent system design. According to LCA, the SO_x emission ratio, which shows that CNTs emit 37.208 times more SO_x than pumice per unit of treatment, is one of the study's most significant numerical results. Notwithstanding their greater adsorption efficiency, this extreme figure emphasizes the substantial environmental burden connected to the manufacture of CNTs. This study's results indicate that pumice is an effective, low-cost, and eco-friendly adsorbent for TC removal. Future studies should concentrate on incorporating pumice-based adsorption systems into hybrid treatment technologies, such as coupling adsorption with biological processes, in order to bridge the gap between laboratory-scale results and real-world applications. Examining the synergy between pumice's adsorption capacity and microbial degradation could significantly improve overall treatment performance, especially for persistent antibiotics like TC. The best circumstances for microbial colonization on pumice should be investigated, along with the long-term performance of bio-adsorptive systems under different conditions, and their scalability in pilot-scale applications.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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